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THE CHOICE OF MATERIAL AND DESIGN FOR A REUSABLE BIONIC FILTER

Abstract. The paper proposes the design of a reusable bionic filter based on the whale's whisker principle and selects an economical polymeric material for its manufacture. The filter design consists of plate segments and small tendrils that provide mechanical water purification. The filter is aimed at reducing water pollution.

The paper compares polymeric materials and selects the best material for a reusable bionic filter based on the whalebone principle

Keywords: *3D model, whale whisker, polymeric materials, bionic filter, mechanical cleaning, water treatment.*

Every day, humanity creates more and more garbage that ends up in oceans, seas, rivers, lakes and other water bodies, polluting them, and therefore reusable water filters are needed to solve this problem. Water purification requires industrial and household filters with different types and degrees of water purification. There are many types of filters. The most popular are mechanical filters, which can be multi-stage and purify a suspension of different fractions.

In this work, a bionic filter is proposed that will function on the principle of a whale's whisker. The filter design consists of segments, the 3D model of which is shown in Figure 1, which repeats the shape of the whale's whisker plate. Each segment is a plate with small hairs.

Figure 1 - Example of segments with and without hairs

The design of the filter assumes that these segments will be combined into sets of several pieces - sections, as shown in Figure 2 (shown without hairs). The sets of segments in the structure are connected to the base and create a cluster. Figure 3 shows a structure with two clusters. To increase the quality of filtering, the segments on the base are staggered. They will be connected to the base by means of grooves. The design of the base can look like a rigid or flexible substrate.

Figure 2 - Example of combined segments

Figure 3 - Example of clusters, base and grooves

To manufacture the working part of the filter, it is planned to use 3D printing or extrusion. These methods will automate the filter production process.

The filter working part will be manufactured using a polymeric material. This material must have the following properties: high chemical resistance, strength, flexibility, affordability, the ability to be moulded using 3D printing or extrusion, and be safe for humans.

The following materials are suitable for these criteria: polyurethane (TPU), polyethylene (PE), polycarbonate (PC), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), polysulfone (PSU). Their mechanical characteristics are given in Table 1 [1].

Table 1 – Mechanical characteristics of polymeric materials

Mechanical characteristics	Materials				
	TPU	PE	PC	HDPE	PSU
Density, g/cc	<u>0,970 - 1,20</u>	0,91 - 0,96	<u>1,03 - 1,26</u>	<u>0,933 - 1,27</u>	<u>1,13 - 1,66</u>
Hardness, Rockwell R	85 - 98	38,0 - 68,0 (Shore D)	114 - 124	80,0 - 112	110 - 127
Flexural Yield Strength, MPa	25 - 50	7 - 16	<u>36,0 - 103</u>	<u>16,5 - 91,0</u>	<u>71,0 - 255</u>
Compressive Yield Strength, MPa	10 - 15	5 - 10	<u>18,0 - 86,2</u>	10 - 20	<u>13,0 - 176</u>
Processing Temperature, °C	190 - 230	<u>145 - 340</u>	260 - 310	<u>180 - 255</u>	<u>80,0 - 420</u>
Nozzle Temperature, °C	200 - 240	<u>204 - 218</u>	270 - 320	<u>210 - 260</u>	<u>335 - 380</u>
Melt Temperature, °C	190 - 225	<u>150 - 220</u>	<u>250 - 343</u>	<u>124 - 321</u>	<u>260 - 410</u>
Mold Temperature, °C	30 - 50	20 - 70	<u>60,0 - 120</u>	<u>15,6 - 65,6</u>	<u>65,6 - 210</u>

Assuming that all the proposed materials are safe for humans, have the necessary physical properties and can be processed using 3D printing and extrusion, the cost of the material will also play an important role in the choice of material. The average cost per kilogram is shown in Table 2 [2-3]. After analysing the cost of polymeric materials, we choose PE for the manufacture of the filter structure.

Table 2 – Comparative cost of polymeric materials

Materials	TPU	PE	PC	HDPE	PSU
Average price (EUR/kg)	1,06	0,25	0,96	1,24	3,20

Thus, the paper proposes the concept of a reusable bionic filter based on the whalebone principle. The filter design consists of segments that mimic whalebone plates, combined into clusters and

staggered for more efficient filtration. In addition, the characteristics of the materials and their relative cost for the manufacture of the working part of the filter were compared. For this purpose, it is advisable to use polyethylene, as it meets all the requirements, including being non-toxic to humans and being economically viable. The introduction of such a filter can significantly improve the quality of water treatment in domestic and industrial settings, contributing to the solution of the problem of water pollution.

References

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